

FORMULATION AND IN-VITRO EVALUATION OF HERBAL SOAP FOR ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY

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Abstract

Objective: The aim and objective of the present work was to formulate herbal soaps and to evaluate organoleptic, physico-chemical, stability and anti-microbial properties. The herbal soaps using Neem, Tulsi, and Aloe vera were formulated for their potential benefits on skin health and antimicrobial activity.

Methods: The herbal soaps were formulated using Melt-and-Pour method to uniformly incorporate the ingredients, to produce a smooth texture soap that exhibits good physico-chemical and anti-microbial properties. The ingredients included extracts of medicinal herbs, different soap bases, preservative and natural fragrances. The soaps were evaluated using various parameters, including organoleptic, physico-chemical, stability and anti-microbial parameters. Physico-chemical evaluation, mainly revealed alcohol insoluble matter, total fatty matter (TFM) and moisture content (MC). Anti-microbial properties were evaluated using agar well diffusion method.

Results: A comparative study of the various properties of the herbal soaps with the marketed soaps was carried out, where the herbal soaps showed similar or better values than the marketed ones. Herbal soaps showed exceptional anti-microbial activity against the bacterial and fungal strains of *Escherichia coli* and *Candida albicans*, *Aspergillus Niger*, respectively.

Conclusion: The soaps were prepared using all herbal and natural ingredients to make it safer to use than the commercial ones, yet providing the same amount of anti-microbial activity. The prepared soap were standardized by evaluating various physico-chemical properties such as organoleptic, physicochemical and anti-microbial activities, in which they exhibited satisfactory values. The phytochemicals present in the herbs strengthen, nourish and moisturise the skin. The herbal soaps serve as good choice for people of all age, with skin that is reactive to most synthetic chemical skin products.

Keywords: Herbal soap, Natural ingredients, Skin health, Anti-microbial activity, Skin compatibility.

INTRODUCTION

Personal factors such as health, lifestyle, work, environment, and maintenance can impact the beauty of skin and hair. Prolonged heat exposure throughout the summer can cause skin dryness, leading to wrinkles, freckles, pimples, pigmentation, and sunburn ^[1]. Cleaning products are used to remove dirt, bacteria, stains, and unpleasant odors from the body to maintain health and beauty. Soaps have a long history of use in our daily lives dating back over 6,000 years. Soaps and detergents serve as disinfectants and are essential for daily hygiene. Soaps Commercial soap often contains dangerous chemicals such plastics, aluminium, barium, mercury, and bisphenol. These compounds, when vaporized or absorbed through the skin, can have negative health effects ^[2]. Medicinal soaps incorporate synthetic or natural bioactive ingredients to the soap base, providing a broad variety of biological action. In recent years, plant-based natural goods have gained popularity as a natural ingredient to enhance medicinal soap's biological qualities ^[8-11].

Synthetic chemicals in medicinal soap product are avoided due to their bad consequences. Replacing synthetic foaming agents like sodium lauryl sulphate with saponins, synthetic anti-bacterial agents like Triclosan with natural ones, and synthetic antioxidants like Butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT) with natural phenolic compounds can reduce side effects from medicinal soaps ^[8-11]. A herbal soap preparation is a pharmaceutical formulation with anti-bacterial and anti-fungal properties. Plant parts, such as leaves, stems, roots, and fruits, are used to treat diseases and maintain health ^[7]. Common constituents in skin care products, such as medicinal soaps, include neem, tulsi, aloe vera, coffee, eucalyptus oil, tea tree oil, coconut oil, olive oil, turmeric, sandalwood, jasmine, and lemon essence ^[8-11].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Neem leaves, Tulsi leaves, Aloe vera gel, Benzoic acid, Glycerin soap base, Goat milk soap base, Fragrances (Fruity autumn, Orchid Vanilla, Orchid Vanilla V₃, Elderflower poney, Seaweed, Floral Garden V₂, Peony Rose ND, Woodland Spice), Methanol, Chloroform, Peptone, Beef extract, Sodium chloride, Agar, Dextrose, Escherichia coli strain, Fungal strains (C. albicans, A. niger)

Methods

Plant Collection and Preparation

Neem (*Azadirachta indica*)

Fresh neem leaves were collected locally, washed, and then shade-dried for 10 days. The dried leaves were coarsely powdered using a mixer grinder and stored in airtight containers until further use.

Tulsi (*Ocimum tenuiflorum*)

Fresh Tulsi leaves were collected locally and shade-dried for 10 days. The dried leaves were pulverized using a mixer grinder and stored in airtight containers.

Aloe vera (*Aloe barbadensis*)

Fresh Aloe vera pods were collected locally. The pods were cut open, and the gel was manually separated using a sterile spatula and used immediately for further studies.

Extraction Methods

Method I: Maceration

Neem and Tulsi leaf powders were extracted using a hydro-organic solvent system (distilled water: chloroform, 70:30).

Neem extraction:

Accurately weighed neem leaf powder (54.3 g) was macerated with 280 mL distilled water and 120 mL chloroform in a covered container. The mixture was agitated intermittently and allowed to stand for 3 days at room temperature. The extract was filtered using Whatman filter paper, and the filtrate was concentrated on a hot water bath. The dried extract was cooled in a desiccator and weighed.

Tulsi extraction:

Tulsi leaf powder (4.90 g) was macerated with 110 mL distilled water and 40 mL chloroform following the same procedure as described for neem. The dried extract was collected, desiccated, and weighed.

Method II: Soxhlet Extraction

Solubility Study

Preliminary solubility studies of neem and Tulsi powders were carried out using methanol, chloroform, and distilled water. Both plant powders showed higher solubility in methanol; hence, methanol was selected as the solvent for Soxhlet extraction.

Soxhlet Extraction Procedure

Dried neem and tulsi leaf powders were placed in a thimble prepared from Whatman filter paper and loaded into the Soxhlet extraction chamber. Methanol (350 mL) was added to a round-bottom flask and heated using a heating mantle. The extraction was carried out at methanol's boiling point (64.7 °C) for 5 hours. The solvent repeatedly condensed and siphoned back into the flask, ensuring continuous extraction of phytoconstituents.

Solvent Evaporation

The methanolic extract obtained from Soxhlet extraction was concentrated using a rotary evaporator under reduced pressure. The solvent was recovered in a collector flask, and the concentrated extract was cooled and stored under refrigeration for further analysis.

Formulation of Herbal Soaps:

S. No.	Ingredients	Formulations (50gm)			Uses
		F1	F2	F3	
1	Soap base	50	50	50	Cleansing agent
2	Extract	3 ml	3 ml	3 ml	Anti-bacterial agent & anti-fungal agent
3	Benzoic acid	0.5 g	0.5 g	0.5 g	Preservative
4	Fragrance	q.s.	q.s.	q.s.	Perfume

FORMULATION OF SOAP:

A mixture of 3ml of Neem/ Tulsi extract/Aloe vera gel, 0.5g of Benzoic acid, 50g of soap base and fragrance (q.s.) were taken to prepare herbal soap.

Procedure:

1. The Soap base (Glycerine) was taken in a beaker and was melted in a hot water bath.
2. Along with the soap base, Neem/ Tulsi extract/Aloe vera gel was added and stirred.
3. Then, Benzoic acid and fragrance was also added and stirred continuously to mix the herbal soap ingredients as mentioned above.
4. It was poured in a soap mould and cooled for 12 hours.

Neem soap

Tulsi soap

Aloe vera soap(glycerine base)

Aloe vera soap(goat milk)

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL EVALUATION

- **pH:**

2 gm of the finished soap was dissolved in 10ml of distilled water, yielding a dissolved sample. A pH meter was used to measure the pH.

- **Foam retention:**

25 millilitre of the 1% soap solution was made and poured into a 100 millilitre measuring cylinder. Then, it was shaken ten times. For four to five minutes, the volume of foam was measured every minute.

- **Foam height:**

A sample of soap weighing 0.5 g was obtained and dissolved in 25 millilitres of distilled water. Then, it was put into a 100 ml measuring cylinder and water was added to make up the volume to 50 ml. After giving 25 strokes, the aqueous volume was measured up to 50 ml, and the foam height was measured above the aqueous volume.

- **Total fatty matter:**

By reacting soap with acid in the presence of hot water and measuring the resulting fatty acid, TFM was determined. After dissolving 10 gm of the designed soap in 150 ml of distilled water, the mixture was heated. 20 millilitres of 15% H₂SO₄ (Sulphuric acid) were added to this and heated until a clear solution was achieved. The resulting solution's surface fatty acid was solidified by heating it once again and adding 7 gm of beeswax. It was then permitted to cake. After removing the cake, it was blotted dry and weighed using formula.

$$\left(\% \text{ TFM} = \frac{(\text{Weight of the cake} - \text{Weight of the wax}) \text{ in gm}}{\text{Weight of the soap in gm}} \times 100 \right)$$

- **Moisture content:**

For one hour, 10g of the sample under investigation was heated to between 100 and 105°C in a hot air oven. The actual weight of the tarred china dish was then subtracted by weighing the sample and the dish. Using the formula below, the weight of the material was recorded in order to determine the percentage of moisture content.

$$\left(\% \text{ Moisture Content} = \frac{(\text{Wt of dish after drying} - \text{Wt before drying}) \text{ in gm}}{\text{Weight of the sample}} \times 100 \right)$$

Stability studies:

The purpose of determining the stability of the soap is to establish the shelf-life of the soap, determining optimal storage conditions and to identify areas needing improvement in formulation of soap.

Real-time stability testing: Long-term storage of soap and its testing under normal conditions. The formulated soap was stored for 3 months and checked for its stability.

Anti-microbial studies:

The antimicrobial activity of the formulated soaps was evaluated against selected bacterial and fungal strains using the agar well diffusion method.

Test organisms:

- **Bacterium:** *Escherichia coli*
- **Fungi:** *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus niger*

Antimicrobial activity was determined by measuring the zone of inhibition around the wells after incubation.

Method: Agar Well Diffusion Assay

Preparation of media:

Nutrient agar (for *E. coli*) and Sabouraud dextrose agar (SDA) (for fungal strains) were prepared using standard compositions. The media were sterilized by autoclaving at 121 °C (15 lbs pressure) for 15 minutes, poured aseptically into sterile Petri plates, and allowed to solidify.

Inoculation:

The solidified agar plates were uniformly inoculated with the respective microbial cultures using a sterile swab.

Well formation:

Wells of uniform diameter (6–8 mm) were punched aseptically in the agar using a sterile cork borer.

Sample preparation and application:

The soap sample was dissolved in distilled water to obtain a solution of known concentration. A fixed volume (100 μ L) of the soap solution was introduced into each well. Standard antimicrobial agents—ceftriaxone (antibacterial) and ketoconazole (antifungal)—were used as positive controls.

Incubation:

Bacterial plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours, while fungal plates were incubated at 30 °C for 48–72 hours.

EVALUATION

Antimicrobial activity was assessed by measuring the diameter of the zone of inhibition (in mm) around each well.

Organoleptic evaluation:

S. No.	Organoleptic parameters	Formulations		
		F1	F2	F3
1	Colour	Translucent Amber	Translucent Greenish yellow	Translucent Amber
2	Odour	Sweetish	Aromatic	Warm woody
3	Appearance	Smooth texture	Smooth texture	Smooth texture

Physico-chemical parameters:

S.No	Parameters	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	Marketed product
1	pH	8.96	8.0	8.2	8.9
2	Foam Height	85ml	80ml	83ml	86ml
3	Foam Retention	7 mins	8 mins	6 mins	7 mins

4	Alcohol Insoluble Matter	16.8%	17%	17.4%	15%
5	Total Fatty Matter	70%	72%	70%	80%
6	Moisture Content	13.2%	10.3%	12.6%	10%
7	Solubility	Soluble	Soluble	Soluble	Soluble

Anti-microbial activity of herbal soaps:

Aloe vera		Neem		Tulsi	
Anti - bacterial activity	Anti - fungal activity	Anti - bacterial activity	Antifungal activity	Antibacterial activity	Antifungal activity
✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Stability studies:

The soaps were tested for real-time stability studies for 3 months. They were still dry, smooth, stable and had no colour change. They still had foaming nature and good cleansing activity. They were gentle on the skin and no rough texture.

DISCUSSION

The present work is concerned with the formulation of soaps using Neem, Tulsi, Aloe vera extracts. The formulated soap was a dry, stable solid, showing no colour change and good appearance, with foamy nature. It was tested for physical and chemical properties. It showed good cleansing activity and caused no irritation.

The pH of the soap was checked and was found to be within the range of 8-9, which is within the optimal range. The foam height and foam retention when compared with the marketed soap showed similar values.

Total fatty matter is the key indicator of the quality of the soap. As the percent of Total fatty matter of our soap is high, the soap has good cleansing properties.

Alcohol insoluble matter was used to assess the quality and purity of soap by identifying the substances that do not dissolve in ethanol. As our soap has less percent of alcohol insoluble matter, the impurities are less. Thus, the formulated soap has good moisturizing properties.

Moisture content of the soap was evaluated, and was found to be near to the values obtained using marketed soap. Our soap had less moisture content, which made it stable over a long period of time.

The soap was tested for cleansing activity and it readily formed globules around the oil particles, making it homogenous with water.

CONCLUSION:

The natural ingredients found in herbal soap have anti-bacterial, anti-fungal, and anti-inflammatory properties, which make the skin effective in various kinds of skin conditions like acne, pimple, eczema, and psoriasis.

Neem, Tulsi and Aloe vera were studied, along with their extraction procedures. The soaps were prepared using all herbal and natural ingredients to make it safer to use

than the commercial ones, yet providing the same amount of anti-microbial activity. The handling of the materials were taken care of by following standard laboratory procedures.

Furthermore, the prepared soaps were standardized by evaluating various physicochemical properties such as organoleptic, physicochemical and anti-microbial activities, in which they exhibited satisfactory values.

The phytochemicals present in the herbs strengthen, nourish and moisturise the skin. The herbal soaps serve as good choice for people of all age, with skin that is reactive to most synthetic chemical skin products.

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